

ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' DENTAL HEALTH AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH STUDENTS' QUALITY OF LIFE

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Abstract. This article discusses the problems of oral cavity diseases in students, including dental diseases and their impact on the quality of life, prevention, causes of the disease. In addition, the most effective solution for the prevention of these diseases is based on analysis and opinions that the main criterion is to follow a healthy lifestyle and hygiene.

Keywords: orthopedics, sociological research, dental health, factors, model, hygiene.

ОЦЕНКА СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ СТУДЕНТОВ И ЕГО ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ С КАЧЕСТВОМ ЖИЗНИ СТУДЕНТОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются проблемы заболеваний полости рта у студентов, в том числе стоматологических заболеваний и их влияние на качество жизни, профилактика, причины возникновения заболевания. Кроме того, наиболее эффективное решение профилактики этих заболеваний основано на анализе и мнении, что главным критерием является соблюдение здорового образа жизни и гигиены.

Ключевые слова: ортопедия, социологические исследования стоматологическое здоровье, факторы, модель, гигиены.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, researchers note the high prevalence and intensity of dental caries among student youth, low level of oral hygiene, in which signs of periodontal tissue damage are more often detected [1,3]. According to experts, the body of young people is more often exposed to the influence of various exogenous and endogenous factors, which leads to an increase in dental diseases. The state of dental health of students is adversely affected by medical and social factors: a diet with excess carbohydrates, low medical literacy of students, student absence from medical examinations, lack of oral sanitation, irregular preventive measures, ignorance of teeth brushing techniques [4,5].

There is evidence that poor dental health reduces the quality of life of students. According to some authors [6], more than 40% of university students have dental problems that negatively affect their quality of life. Defects of the dental system impair the communication skills of students, cause speech defects and cosmetic problems, and cause bad breath, which affects the vital activity and emotional state of students [7, 8].

Sociological studies show that there is currently a dissonance between the declared value of health and the unwillingness to take real action to preserve it. Knowing that dental health affects the quality of life and that oral hygiene is important, most citizens do not observe it [9]. Even professional knowledge of the rules for personal hygiene does not affect the level of dental health and oral hygiene [10,14].

In connection with the above, there is a need to develop a comprehensive system of treatment and preventive measures to improve the dental health of students, taking into account the criteria for effective prevention of diseases of hard dental tissues [11].

Purpose of the study. To study the dental health of students and show its impact on the quality of life of students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The survey assessed the dental health of student youth. The results of the answers to the question "How often do you visit the dentist?" show that 67.0% of respondents visit the doctor as needed, if they have anxiety or pain in the oral cavity; 30.0% seek dental care regularly (once every six months); 3.0% very rarely visit a dentist or orthodontist.

It is worth paying attention to the emotional state of students on the eve of a visit to a dental clinic. The survey showed that 55.0% of respondents do not experience any anxiety about dental treatment. 32.0% of respondents experience slight fear and anxiety, and 13.0% of students feel extremely anxious. The frequency of the hygiene procedure was determined based on the answers to the question "Do you brush your teeth regularly?" It was found that two thirds of students (75.0%) comply with oral hygiene requirements and regularly brush their teeth in the morning and evening. Once a day - in the morning or in the evening - they brush their teeth, respectively, 17.0 and 5.0% of the respondents answered that they do not brush their teeth every day, but only as needed.

Let's consider the priorities when choosing toothpastes. About half of the students (47.5%) prefer to brush their teeth with whitening toothpaste. The second most popular is toothpaste for sensitive teeth. These types of pastes are used by 23.4% of students. Anti-caries, anti-inflammatory and salt toothpastes are used by 16.5; 10.6 and 2.0% of students, respectively.

Next, we were interested in what toothpastes the students prefer to brush their teeth with. Answers to the question "What brand of toothpaste do you use?" indicate that 42.0% of respondents prefer to use Colgate toothpaste; 15.7% - Blend-A-med; 15.1% - Splat. Other toothpastes (Lacalut, Lesnoy Balsam, Black Pearl) are less popular with students. It is obvious that the component composition of toothpastes from well-established manufacturers helps strengthen tooth enamel and prevents tooth decay. We have found that 94.4% of students do not have orthopedic structures in their oral cavity, only 5.0% of students have dental crowns.

The students were asked to do a self-analysis of oral diseases. To the question "Do you currently have any oral diseases?" 73.0% of respondents answered that they were fine and had no oral diseases; a quarter of the students believed that they had problems with their gums. At the time of the examination, 61.3% of the students had all their teeth healthy, and 38.7% had teeth that required treatment. The survey did not reveal any serious changes in the condition of the teeth and gums of the students surveyed.

During the further survey, we were able to establish the number of filled and extracted teeth in the respondents: 1-2 filled teeth - 38.8% of respondents; 3-5 - 36.9%; 70.0% of respondents do not have extracted teeth; 30.0% have incomplete upper and lower dental arches (1-3 teeth removed). About half of the students (49.0%) have a correct bite, 18.6% of respondents have an abnormal bite, and 32.4% of respondents have no idea about this pathology and found it difficult to answer the question.

To the question "Do you think there is a relationship between the condition of the oral cavity and the quality of life in terms of nutrition and speech?" 83.5% of students (the vast majority) answered "Yes", and 16.5% - "No". It is obvious that the level of students' comfort in society is affected by dental health. 89.0% of students did not have speech disorders due to dental problems, 6.6% had them, but now they are fixed, and 4.4% have speech disorders. 62.7% of students agree that the condition of the oral cavity depends on proper nutrition, 31.8% of students

believe that the condition of the dental apparatus partially depends on rational nutrition, and 5.5% of respondents do not see such a dependence at all.

When examining the nutritional characteristics of students, we found the following. Half of the students (50.5%) eat baked goods and sweets, while 49.5% of respondents prefer to include vegetables and fruits in their diet. Eating a lot of carbohydrates and not taking proper care of the oral cavity often lead to the deposition of soft and sticky substances on the teeth. The survey results show that 60.8% of respondents sometimes have plaque on their teeth; 33.0% do not have plaque on their teeth; 6.2% have constant plaque formation.

The last question of the questionnaire concerned the students' well-being in connection with the condition of their oral cavity. 63.7% of students answered: "I feel confident, I have beautiful teeth." 23.5% of university and college students experience discomfort and tension during conversations with others due to defects in the dentition. 12.8% of students are indifferent to the aesthetic condition of the oral cavity. Based on previously obtained data [17] and the results of the assessment of dental health, it can be said with confidence that numerous risk factors negatively lead to the development of oral diseases. A comparative analysis of the obtained data allowed us to develop a model of students' dental health, which is an integral part of public health. Dental health is determined by numerous medical, biological, hygienic and behavioral factors. The social well-being of a person in society is directly related to the aesthetic and speech function of the oral cavity and affects the quality of life. In turn, the quality of life associated with health is an integral characteristic of the physical, psychological and social state.

CONCLUSION

As the results of the study showed, the dental health of students is generally satisfactory. Most students visit the dentist only when absolutely necessary and without much concern. Students, as a rule, comply with oral hygiene requirements and prefer whitening toothpastes. Most of the respondents use Colgate toothpaste, they do not have serious changes in the condition of the tissues of the teeth and gums. The dentition usually contains from 1-2 to 3-5 filled teeth and 1-3 extracted teeth. Half of the students have a diet dominated by sweet foods, which leads to the formation of soft plaque on the crowns of the teeth.

A significant proportion of respondents (83.5%) indicate a relationship between the condition of the oral cavity and the quality of life, and 60.8% of respondents consider their teeth beautiful and therefore feel confident. Thus, it should be noted that dental health is an integral part of public health. It depends on numerous medical and biological factors, lifestyle and systematic use of oral hygiene products. In turn, the aesthetic condition of the oral cavity and the absence of speech difficulties due to dental problems ensures a person's social well-being.

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